

EXPLORING TRADITIONAL FOOD PRESERVATION METHODS OF WOLAITA PEOPLE, ETHIOPIA

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ABSTRACT: Postharvest food loss is significant in developing countries like Ethiopia, contributing to food insecurity. To address this issue, it is essential to leverage indigenous knowledge and practices related to food processing, preservation, and storage. This study assessed indigenous food preservation techniques among rural household heads in Wolaita Zone, Ethiopia. Using a cross-sectional survey design, 384 household heads were randomly selected and consented to collect data via structured questionnaires and observational checklists. The results indicated that 61.5% of respondents regularly preserve raw foods, 20.6% preserve cooked foods, and 16.7% preserve perishable items. The most commonly employed preservation methods were sun drying (33%), salting (23%), heating (18%), packing (9%), cooling (7%), fermentation (6%), and smoking (4%). Chi-square tests revealed significant associations between cooked food preservation and demographic factors such as sex, age, education, occupation, and monthly income ($p < .005$). Similar associations were observed for raw and perishable foods, highlighting the influence of demographics on preservation practices. The study reveals a significant association between food preservation practices and demographic characteristics. Sun drying, salting, and heating were the most prevalent methods for food preservation in the study area. A significant portion of participants did not practice food preservation methods, indicating the need for education and awareness. Indigenous food preservation methods within cultural context are vital to reduce postharvest food losses and ensure food security. Efforts should be made to promote traditional practices, which not only enhance food preservation but also contribute to cultural heritage and food security.

Keywords: Ethiopia, Food, Indigenous knowledge, Preservation, Wolaita.

INTRODUCTION

Ethiopia, the second-most populous country in Africa, grapples with a significant food deficit and alarming levels of food insecurity, affecting approximately 33 million people who suffer from chronic undernourishment, predominantly among rural residents who lack the resources to produce, purchase, or

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properly store food (FAO, 2014; Kuyu and Bereka, 2020). This dire situation is exacerbated by widespread poverty, with many individuals unable to meet their minimum nutritional requirements (Endalew et al., 2015). The rates of child malnutrition are particularly concerning, marked by high levels of stunting, underweight, and wasting (CSA, 2014).

Food insecurity in Ethiopia is not merely a consequence of inadequate food production; it is significantly compounded by high postharvest food losses, which are largely attributed to limited capacities for food processing and preservation (Kuyu and Tola, 2018). The postharvest losses vary widely among different food types, influenced by factors such as food characteristics, climatic conditions, and management practices. Unprocessed foods can be categorized into perishables and durables, with perishables including fruits, vegetables, dairy, and meats being particularly vulnerable to rapid deterioration (Teferra, 2022). In contrast, dry grains like cereals and pulses, while more stable; still face risks from pests and other factors (Teferra, 2022).

Extensive studies highlight the severity of postharvest losses in Ethiopia, with estimates ranging from 15% for cereal crops to as high as 80% for fruits and vegetables, and 40% for milk and its products (Getachew, 2003; Kuyu and Tola, 2018; Kuyu and Bereka, 2020). Addressing these losses is crucial for improving food security, and this can be achieved by recognizing and leveraging indigenous knowledge, skills, and practices in food processing, preservation, and storage (Asogwa et al., 2017). Indigenous knowledge, which encompasses practices honed over generations, has proven adaptable and innovative, offering sustainable solutions to combat hunger and malnutrition (World Bank, 1998; Oniang'o, 2004).

In Ethiopia, traditional food handling, preparation, and preservation methods represent a rich repository of knowledge that has been passed down through generations (Ethiopian Herald, cited in Kuyu and Tola, 2018). These practices not only provide accessible and sustainable food preservation methods but also reinforce cultural identity. By valuing and integrating indigenous knowledge systems, local communities can actively contribute to their food security strategies. However, documentation of these traditional

preservation methods remains scarce, with existing research primarily focusing on milk and dairy products (Fita et al., 2005; Alemu and Girma, 2018; Tola et al., 2018). There is a notable gap in research concerning traditional food preservation methods across various food types, such as raw food, cooked food, and easily spoiled foods, particularly in the Wolaita zone of southern Ethiopia, despite the region's rich diversity of traditional foods. Culturally, Wolaita is home to the Wolaita people, who possess a rich heritage and unique traditions. Traditional foods play a crucial role in the cultural identity of the Wolaita people and are regularly consumed, especially during celebrations and festivals (<https://wolaita.gov.et/en/>).

Therefore, this study aims to assess the indigenous food preservation techniques among residents of rural areas in the suburbs of Sodo town, Wolaita, southern Ethiopia. The findings will provide valuable insights for stakeholders seeking to enhance food security by modernizing and promoting the broader application of indigenous food preservation methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The study was conducted from March 2018 to April 2018 in the rural kebeles of Sodo Zuria Woreda, Wolaita Zone, Ethiopia. Geographically, Wolaita Zone is situated between 7° N and 37° 45' E. It is bordered by the Central Ethiopia region to the north, the Sidama Region to the east, the Gamo and Gofa Zones to the south, the Southwest Ethiopia region to the west, and the Oromia Region to the northeast. The total area of the zone is 451,170 hectares. Sodo Zuria Woreda is one of the 16 rural Woredas and seven town administrations in Wolaita Zone. Its administrative center is Sodo town, located 383 km from Addis Ababa, the capital city of Ethiopia. According to data from the Sodo Zuria Woreda office, the total area of Sodo Zuria is 38,040 hectares. Administratively, Sodo Zuria Woreda is divided into 25 kebeles, comprising five urban kebeles and twenty rural kebeles. This study focused on three rural kebeles (Wachigabusha, Wajakero, and Tomegerera) out of the 20 rural kebeles in Sodo Zuria Woreda

Figure 1. Map of the study location, Sodo Zuria Woreda, south Ethiopia regional state, Ethiopia.

Study design

A community-based cross-sectional study design was applied to document the indigenous knowledge about food preservation techniques and the type of food the community preserved by using the indigenous techniques at the household level among Sodo zuria rural kebeles.

Sample size determination

From 20 rural kebeles in Sodo Zuria Woreda, 3 kebeles were randomly selected. These were Wachigabusha, Wajakero, and Tomegerera. Then the sample size was determined according to Cochran's (1963) single population proportion sampling technique;

$$n = \frac{z^2 pq}{d^2}$$

Where:

n = minimum sample size

z = standard normal deviate 95% (1.96)

q = $1-p$ (probability not included in sample size 50% (0.5))

d = tolerance error of margin set at 0.05.

The calculated samples were 384.

Sampling procedure

In consultation with the Wolaita Zone Administration, Sodo Zuria Woreda (District) was purposively selected due to its reliance on traditional methods for food preservation. From the 20 kebeles in Sodo Zuria Woreda, 3 kebeles were randomly selected for the survey. The calculated sample population of 384 was equally allocated among the three kebeles, with each receiving a sample size of 128. A total of 384 heads of households voluntarily participated in the study.

Each household was selected using a lottery sampling method, where numbers were assigned to each household, corresponding to a subject. Participants were then recruited after obtaining their consent to take part in the study. In addition to the 384 heads of households, 30 key informants (10 from each kebele) were selected with the assistance of district administrative offices, peasant association leaders, district culture and tourism offices, and local elders. For each traditional preservation method, the informants were asked to list and explain the types of food they prepare at home, the preservation methods they use, the procedures they follow, and the ingredients they add.

Data collection and analysis

Data were collected from 384 households using closed-ended or structured questionnaires, along with open-ended questions for key informants to document the detailed processes of the indigenous food preservation techniques. The close ended questionnaire contained two sections; socio-demographic characteristics (Sex,

educational level, occupation, monthly income and age) data was largely presented using descriptive statistics in tables displaying summary values, frequency, and percentages. All data were analyzed using SPSS version 21 software to determine the association of the demographic characteristics and practice of traditional food preservative techniques and statistical significance was determined by considering cut of value $p < 0.005$.

RESULTS

Socio-demographic backgrounds of the study subjects

A total of 384 heads of households were included in the study. Of these, 262 (68.23%) were female and 122 (31.77%) were male (Table 1). The majority of the respondents (111 or 28.9%) were in the age group of 36-45 years old, followed by 26-35 years old (91 or 23.7%) and 15-25 years old (73 or 19%). The number of respondents above 45 years old was 109 (28.4%). With regard to educational status, the majority of the respondents (213 or 55.47%) were illiterate, 106 (27.6) of them were at primary school levels, 52 (13.5%) at secondary school levels and only 13 (3.4%) of the respondents had higher education levels.

Occupationally, the predominant proportion of the respondents were farmers (185 or 48.2%) and merchants (116 or 30.2%), followed by daily laborers (72 or 18.8%) with only 11(2.3%) civil servants. Most of the respondents (243 or 63.3%) said their monthly income didn't exceed ETB 500 and only 30 (7.8%) of the respondents said their monthly income exceeded ETB 700.

Table 1. Socio-demographic backgrounds of the heads of the households in Sodo Zuria.

Socio-demographic variable		Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	122	31.77
	Female	262	68.23
Age group	15 -25	73	19.01
	26 - 35	91	23.69
	36 - 45	111	28.91
	46 - 55	62	16.14
	>55	47	12.24
Educational levels	Illiterate	213	55.47
	Primary school	106	27.60
	Secondary school	52	13.54
	Certificate	2	0.52
	Diploma	7	1.82
	Degree	4	1.04
Occupation	Daily labor	72	18.75
	Farmer	185	48.18
	Merchant	116	30.21
	Government employee	11	2.86
Monthly income (birr)*	200 - 500	243	63.28
	500 - 700	111	28.90
	>700	30	7.81

1 USD = 28.45 Birr (2018 exchange rate)

Practice of indigenous food preservation methods among the study subjects

Out of the 384 participants, 61.46% reported always preserving raw food items in their homes, while 20.57% always preserved cooked food items, and 16.67% always preserved perishable foods (Table 2).

Table 2. Practice of traditional food preservative methods in Sodo Zuria woreda, Southern Ethiopia

Variable	Response	Frequency	%
Do you preserve cooked food items in your home?	Yes	79	20.57
	No	305	79.43
Do you preserve raw food items in your home?	Yes.	236	61.46
	No	148	38.54
Do you preserve easily spoiled foods in your home?	Yes	64	16.67
	No	320	81.25

To examine the relationships between indigenous food preservation methods and various demographic characteristics, a chi-square test of association was conducted. This statistical test assesses whether

significant relationships exist between two categorical variables. The results demonstrated significant associations across multiple dimensions. Specifically, the chi-square tests revealed significant relationships between the preservation of cooked foods and demographic factors such as sex, age, education, occupation, and monthly income ($p < .005$). Similar associations were identified for raw and spoiled food items, indicating the influence of demographic characteristics on preservation practices (Table 3).

Table 3. Chi-Square test results for associations between demographic characteristics and indigenous food preservation practices.

Variable	Chi-Square (X ²)	Degrees of Freedom (df)	p-value
Cooked Food Items			
Sex	213.5	1	< .005
Age	384.1	4	< .005
Educational Level	79.850	5	< .005
Occupation	342.7	3	< .005
Monthly Income	57.7	2	< .005
Raw Food Items			
Sex	112.1	1	< .005
Age	277.2	4	< .005
Educational Level	307.9	5	< .005
Occupation	305.4	3	< .005
Monthly Income	355.2	2	< .005
Spoiled Food Items			
Sex	166.1	1	< .005
Age	384.1	4	< .005
Educational Level	359.8	5	< .005
Occupation	609.1	3	< .005
Monthly Income	138.2	2	< .005

Traditional food processing and preservation methods used in the study community

The heads of the households were asked about the types of foods that they often found highly perishable and the preservation techniques they used. The responses they gave to the question regarding the methods and the preserved food items are summarized in Figure 2 and 3, respectively. The most commonly used preservation method was sun drying (126 or 33%) followed by salting (87 or 23%), heating (69 or 18%),

packing or storing in covered containers (34 or 9%), cooling or low temperature storage (28 or 7%), fermentation (24 or 6%) and smoking (16 or 4%) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Preservation techniques and number of the respondents that used the preservation method in Sodo Zuria woreda, Southern Ethiopia.

Figure 3. Types of traditional food items and corresponding indigenous preservation methods used among residents of Sodo Zuria woreda, Southern Ethiopia.

The detailed account of the methods and their respective applications was narrated by key informants, who were elder members of the study subjects included in the research. From the recorded seven indigenous food preservation methods, the detailed application of the most widely used methods, such as sun drying, packing/canning, salting, and fermentation, was narrated by the key informants. Some of the methods are not used alone but rather play a role in other preservation methods. For example, salting was reported to be used in combination with smoking, and heating and cooling can be applied in various preservation methods as part of the preservation process. Thus, the methods described below only include some of the standalone indigenous food preservation methods.

Sun drying

Drying by sunlight was said to be applied to a wide range of food items like cereals (maize, barely), root crops, and vegetables (cassava, yam, and pumpkin cucumber) (Figure 3). Maize often is dried in the sun and stored in a woody or bamboo container fumigated with some chemical pesticides (Figure 4D). Similarly, barely is also stored in tight bamboo baskets or local big jars after harvesting (Figure 4D). Among the most common staple root crops preserved by drying in the study community, cassava and yam were the principal ones mentioned. Cassava is preserved after first removing the bark and chopping it into small pieces with knives. Subsequently, the comminuted pieces are dried in the sun and then packed into local containers and stored inside the home (Figure 4, C1 to C4). Yam, cucumber, and pumpkins are also preserved likewise after ripening; they are dried, packed in a woody box, and stored under cool shades outside the home.

Packaging/Canning

According to the respondents, packing or canning is used as a means of preserving various local foods, such as Kocho (uncha), cheese with meat or kinche (logumuwa), bulla (etema), etema with cheese (Muchuwa), chopped meat with plus spice and butter (guguwa), and dat'a (berbere) (Figure 3). Packaging raw or cooked food items with locally made baskets, clay pots, jars, and plastic cans was practiced widely in the study community. For example, one popular dish in the community called 'logumuwa' is prepared from dehulled,

coarsely ground barley, which is cooked by boiling with water and seasoned with mixtures of cheese, chopped beef, and spiced butter. The prepared logomuwa as such is then packed in a clay pot or jar (Figure 5A). Similarly, another local food item, ‘etema’ is prepared from the flour of enset (*Ensete ventricosum*) called bulla which is cooked by boiling and seasoned with butter and various spices. The prepared etema is then packed in clay pots or jars similar to logomuwa (Figure 4 B1 to B3). Another popular cooked food prepared and stored between meals is ‘Guguwa’ made from any meat (beef, mutton, or goat meat) that is chopped, cooked by roasting or boiling and seasoned by butter, spice and stored in clay pots (Figure 5C). ‘Muchuwa’ is another popular dish made from cottage cheese (Ayib), cooked ‘etema’ seasoned with butter and salt. It is also prepared and stored between meals in clay pots or jars (Figure 5B).

Figure 4. Plant-based foods produced and preserved using various traditional methods in Sodo Zuria Woreda, Wolaita zone, Ethiopia. **A)** Kocho packed in dry enset leaves. **B1-B3)** Bula (or Etema) packed in enset leaves and plastic containers. **C1-C4)** Cassava pulp with intact bark, peeled, pulverized, and dried, stored in bamboo baskets. **D)** Outdoor bamboo storage bin for dry maize. **E)** Clay pots used for storing barley seeds. **F)** Multipurpose plastic storage bin for dried seeds, flour, and Etema. etc.

Fermentation

Fermentation is another popular food preparation and preservation method identified by the respondents. It is applied mainly to the preparation of fermented dairy products and the principal staple food 'kocho' (Figure 3) made from the pulp of the enset plant. The production of fermented dairy products and 'kocho' fermentation is the same as is done elsewhere in Ethiopia.

For milk preservation, fresh milk is often collected in well-smoked clay pots and left at ambient conditions to undergo natural fermentation by indigenous microorganisms. After one day of fermentation, it forms the traditional sour milk called 'ergo' also locally known as 'meomata'. A considerable amount of milk produced by the household is consumed in the form of 'ergo' or ergo may be used for the production of other dairy products. For example, ergo is churned for the production of traditional butter called 'qibe' and the remaining buttermilk from which most of the butter is separated is further processed by moderate heating of 50 – 70 °C to prepare 'Ayib'. According to key informants, fresh butter separated from the buttermilk is kneaded and washed with cold, salted water that has been boiled earlier. The treated butter is then stored in clay jars (Figure 5F). Ayib is made by heating the buttermilk moderately for about 15 to 20 minutes. Finally, the curd is separated from the whey, and wrapped with enset leaves, on top of it are placed some heavy objects to express the remaining whey from the curd.

Kocho is another important food item other than milk products produced and preserved by fermentation in the study community. It is produced by fermentation of the pulp of pseudostem and corm of enset plant. To make kocho, a pit is dug in the backyard home garden where enset makes the principal component. The inside of the pit is lined with enset leaves to avoid contact with soil and dirt. After the pit is prepared as such, the admixture of pulverized scraps from the fleshy part of the pseudostem and the corm (root part) is filled into the pit. The pulp is overlaid with more enset leaves and a heavy cover is put on top of it to ensure airtight condition. The fermentation may take from months to years and at the end of the fermentation portions are removed from the pit and pressed to remove the liquid part resulting in fibrous moist kocho. To

remove the fiber, the kocho is kneaded and shredded to make it into fine powder which is then wrapped in clean enset leaves and stored until needed for preparation of kocho bread (Figure 4A).

Like kocho, bula (Etema) is also produced from the fermented pulp of enset, only that pulp is derived from the pseudostem rather than admixture from the corm. It is whiter and less fibrous than kocho, often prized nutritious food in the form of gruel and porridge for newly delivered mothers in the study community.

Accompanying meat dishes is a fermented condiment made from chili pepper called data (Figure 3). It is prepared by grinding the green or ripened red chili pepper with a local stone mill manually along with an admixture of garlic and ginger. The mixture is often packed into small jars and allowed to undergo fermentation at ambient conditions (Figure 5D).

Salting and smoking

The preservation of meat, whenever it is available in plenty during the holidays, is of minor importance in the study community. It is cut into thin elongated pieces (Zilzil), salted, and hung on a rope over the fireplace where there is plenty of smoke (Figure 5G).

Figure 5. Partially prepared and ready-to-consume local foods produced and consumed by the community in Sodo Zuria Woreda, Wolaita Zone, Ethiopia. **A)** Logomuwa **B)** Mucho **C)** Guguwa **D)** Data (fermented pepper condiment) **E)** Raw kneaded butter **F)** Refined and spiced butter (ghee) **G)** Salted meat cut into strips for preservation by smoking and drying.

DISCUSSION

This study assessed the indigenous food preservation practices and techniques among residents of rural kebeles of Sodo zuria woreda, Wolaita zone, southern Ethiopia. In the present study, 68.2% of the respondents were female, consistent with the general cultural fact that females are responsible for the preparation of food (Nahusnay and Tessfaye, 2015). With regard to the indigenous food preservation practice among the study participants, 61.46%, 20.57% and 16.67% of the participants preserve raw, cooked, and easily spoiled foods in their homes respectively. Majority of the participants reported some level of practice in indigenous food preservation for raw food items, suggesting a cultural inclination towards preserving raw ingredients. However, the practice of preserving cooked and easily spoiled foods (dairy products, meat, and fermented foods) appears to be less common. This could be due to various factors such as convenience, availability of refrigeration, or cultural preferences for freshly cooked meals. These findings contradicted the reports from Nigeria (Olusanya et al., 2005).

The chi-square test of association revealed that demographic factors such as sex, age, educational level, occupation, and monthly income significantly influenced the likelihood of participants engaging in food preservation practices for cooked, raw, and spoiled food items. Similar patterns emerged for raw and spoiled food items, where significant associations were again found with sex, age, educational level, occupation, and monthly income. These findings indicate the importance of understanding how demographic factors shape food preservation practices among the Wolaita people. By identifying these associations, we can better inform future interventions aimed at promoting traditional food preservation methods, ultimately contributing to improved food security and cultural preservation in the region.

The percentage of respondents who used sun drying, the most commonly used preservation method in the study area, was much lower than the 95% reported from Uganda (Agea et al., 2008) and 80% from Nigeria (Nnadi et al., 2013). Since most disease-causing organisms require a moist environment to survive and multiply, drying is a natural technique for preventing spoilage (Sperber, 2009). Indeed, the act of simply

leaving foods out in the sun and wind to dry out is probably one of the earliest forms of food preservation (Adeyeye, 2017). The sun drying method practiced in the study community included spreading the food item on flat surfaces covered by old linen, plastic sheets, and even on the bare wiped earth. Under such circumstances there is little control of the drying process and the food item would be subject to spoilage from wind-borne dirt, vermin, insects, worms, and the food handlers themselves. Microbial toxins may develop under an uncontrolled drying set up leading to poor quality and reduced edibility. Loss of normal color, flavor and loss of vitamins are some of the most important disadvantages of drying food which can be mitigated by controlled drying (Asogwa et al., 2017).

Next to sun drying the study participants also mentioned various methods of storage of food items in covered containers. This is in agreement with the practice of indigenous people in many parts of Africa (Asogwa et al., 2017). Proper crop storage plays an integral part in ensuring domestic food supply (Thamaga-Chitja et al., 2004) and that seed quality and vigor are maintained (Abba and Lovato, 1999). In the present study packaging raw or cooked food items with locally made baskets, clay pots, jars, and plastic cans was also practiced widely in the study community as mentioned by 34 (9%) of the respondents. Storage facilities not only offer the opportunity to provide a supply of food between staple crop harvests but farmers can improve farm incomes by storing crops and selling at premium prices when demand outstrips supply later in the post-harvest period (Olakojo and Akinlosotu, 2004). Proper storage of cooked food items between meals also plays an important role in preventing food-borne disease outbreaks.

Fermentation (24 or 6%) was also recorded in the present study as one of the means to produce and preserve a wide range of foods like milk, milk products, and kocho. According to Asogwa et al. (2017), Fermented foods are defined as those foods which have been subjected to the action of microorganisms and enzymes for the production of foods with distinct quality attributes that are quite different from the original agricultural raw material.

Fermentation is an important food processing technology usually developed by women in most of Africa and some Asian countries (Asogwa et al., 2017). This fact was demonstrated in the present study where the study community described the production of important fermented foods like fermented dairy products and Kocho which are produced mostly by women and staple food for the majority of people in southern Ethiopia. Fermented vegetable foods are also popular in other parts of Africa. For example, 'Gari'– a fermented cassava and ogi in Nigeria (Sanni et al., 2008).

Milk is a highly perishable food product that is susceptible to adulteration, and its quality is greatly influenced by farm management (Bekele et al., 2015). The community in this study, like many in Ethiopia, preserves milk by processing it into various dairy products through fermentation (Gonfa et al., 2001). They produce sour milk known as 'ergo', which is consumed directly or used to make traditional butter and other products. This highlights the importance of indigenous dairy processing methods in the community (Berhe et al., 2017). Various dairy products, including fresh whole milk, whole sour milk (Ergo), butter, Arera (defatted sour milk), Ayib (a traditional cottage cheese), and nitirkibe (ghee), are majorly produced and consumed in many parts of the country (Kuyu and Bereka, 2020). An extensive review and a detailed description of the production of various dairy products in Ethiopia can be found in Ashenafi (2006). Fermented milk is known to contain high concentrations of probiotics, which offer several health benefits. These include improving intestinal tract health, enhancing the immune system, synthesizing and enhancing nutrient bioavailability, reducing symptoms of lactose intolerance, decreasing allergy prevalence in susceptible individuals, and reducing the risk of certain cancers (Parvez et al., 2006).

Kocho, a food item produced and preserved by fermentation, is an important staple in the southern regions of Ethiopia, including the study area. According to the respondents in the present study, Kocho is made by fermenting the pulp of the pseudostem and corm of the enset plant. The detailed process of making kocho in areas where it is consumed in Ethiopia is similar to the findings of this study. According to Birmeta et al (2019), and Kuyu and Bereka (2020), Kocho is made through the fermentation of enset plant pulp, which

is placed in a pit lined with enset leaves to prevent contact with soil. The mixture of pseudostem and corm scraps is added, covered tightly, and left to ferment for months or years. After fermentation, portions are pressed to remove liquid, resulting in moist kocho. The fiber is then removed, and the kocho is kneaded and shredded into a fine powder, wrapped in enset leaves, and stored for later use in making kocho bread (Tedla and Abebe, 1994). After fermentation, the kocho is often stored in pits lined with enset leaves for a minimum of one month, but it can be stored for several months or even years. This food provides a highly carbohydrate-rich staple food for 35% of Ethiopians living in the southern and southwestern parts of the country (Forsido et al., 2013; Yirmaga, 2013). In addition, a study on antioxidant capacity, total phenolics, and nutritional content in selected Ethiopian staple food ingredients revealed that enset and its products have the potential to develop value-added food products with nutritional and health benefits (Forsido et al., 2013).

Generally, fermentation enhances food security in that it provides a cost-effective method of preserving food, thus making it available during periods of scarcity (Asogwa et al., 2017). It could also contribute to food safety by controlling the growth and multiplication of several pathogens in foods, especially in developing countries where economic problems pose a challenge to food safety.

Smoking and salting were used together to preserve perishable food, such as meat, in the present study community. From the total of 384, 87 and only 16 of the respondents used salting and smoking as the means of food preservation, respectively. These methods are widely used for preserving meat, especially during holidays when it is abundantly available. Traditionally, in Africa, meat is consumed unprocessed. However, in general, meat is preserved by drying, smoking, or salting (Addis, 2015). Similar to the findings of the present study, in many parts of Ethiopia and northern Kenya, meat is cut into long pieces (quanta), smeared with powdered pepper, salted, and dried by hanging it above the fireplace for 5-7 days (Oniang'o et al., 2004). According to Rahman et al. (2023), the compounds present in wood smoke have antimicrobial actions that prevent the growth of spoilage-causing organisms. It is also known that salt binds with water molecules

and acts as a dehydrating agent in foods (Okos et al., 2018). A high level of salinity may also impair the conditions under which pathogens can survive (Durack et al., 2008).

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to assess indigenous food preservation techniques among residents of rural areas in the suburbs of Sodo town, Wolaita, southern Ethiopia. The study identified that a significant portion of participants did not practice food preservation methods, highlighting the need for education and awareness. Sun drying and salting were the most commonly utilized preservation methods. There was also a significant association between the practice of indigenous food preservation and various demographic characteristics. Understanding and valuing these indigenous food preservation practices can contribute to promoting sustainable food preservation and contribute to food security in the region. By recognizing the significance of indigenous preservation methods and their cultural context, efforts can be made to preserve and promote traditional practices that contribute to both food preservation and cultural heritage, while enhancing food security.

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